

THE EFFECT OF MACHINING PARAMETERS ON SURFACE ROUGHNESS USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY (RSM)

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<p>Keywords: Response surface methodology, Parameters, Surface Roughness, Plain carbon steel, Machining, Effect</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>The effect of machining parameters on surface roughness using response surface methodology (RSM) was investigated. The data used for the work was obtained from the previous work titled “effect of machining parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel using lathe machine”. The data was further expanded using the “Rand function” in Microsoft Excel. Five hundred (500) data points were generated from the original data using this function. These data points were used to perform the analyses in response surface methodology. The result revealed that the relative importance of feed rate was 45.91%, cutting speed was 28.94% and depth of cut was 25.15%. The quadratic model was selected to predict the mean surface roughness of the turning operation. The model, F- value of 31.34 implied that the model was significant. Values of “Prob > F” than 0.0500 indicated that model terms were significant, i.e. cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut were all significant effects on the mean surface roughness. The model was significant with a low probability value of 0.0001 and a satisfactory coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.9658$. The high coefficient of determination showed excellent correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable (or response being the mean surface roughness). It was observed that the cutting speed and the depth of cut had a direct relationship with the mean surface roughness, while the feed rate had an indirect relationship on the mean surface roughness. From the results obtained from ANOVA, it was found that cutting speed had the</i></p>
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most significant effect on the mean surface roughness, followed by depth of cut, and the feed rate. At lower values of feed, there was a gradual decrease in the values of surface roughness when the depth of cut was 0.35 mm. Finally the study revealed that with optimal values of cutting parameters of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut at 254.056 (rpm), 0.183419 (mm/rev) and 0.254583 (mm) respectively. Optimal minimum surface roughness was found to be 0.663487 (microns), and a desirability of 1.00 was obtained.

1. INTRODUCTION

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a collection of mathematical and statistical techniques useful for the modelling and analysis of problems in which a response of interest is influenced by several variables and the objective is to optimize the response (Olawoye, 2016). For instance, an engineer or a data analyst may decide to find the levels of force (x_1) and area (x_2) in order to either maximise or minimise the stress involved in the properties of a certain engineering material (y_1).

Olawoye (2016) documented that RSM can be categorised into;

- i. Box-Behnken design
- ii. Central composite design,
- iii. Dohler design and the
- iv. Mixture response surface methodology

Aman and Hari (2005) stated that planning of experiments is particularly very useful in deriving clear and accurate conclusions from the experimental observations. They report that inferences are made from these conclusions and at times, these inferences assist in specifying the methods for collection of data and initiates

techniques for proper interpretation of results obtained from experiments. In cases where inferences drawn from observations are not exact, the need for a mathematical model arises. According to Puneet *et al.*, (2015), the response surface methodology for the optimization of experiments was proposed by G.E.P Box and K.B. Wilson in 1951. RSM was birthed as a result of the fact that in most experimental situations, it is possible to represent independent factors in quantitative form and these factors can be thought of as having a functional relationship or response to the dependent factors. Aman and Hari (2005) reported that for a given set of independent factors, a characteristic surface responds. When the mathematical form of the response surface is not known, it can be satisfactorily approximated within the experimental region by a polynomial. They submitted that the higher the degree of the polynomial, the better the correlation; though at the same time the costs of experimentation become higher. RSM may be applied for developing the mathematical models in the form of multiple regression equations correlating the

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dependent parameters such as cutting force, power consumption, surface roughness, tool life etc. with three independent parameters, viz. cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut, in a turning process. In applying RSM, the dependent parameter is viewed as a surface to which a mathematical model is fitted (Aman and Hari, 2005).

The surface integrity of a machined part encompasses all primary, standard and extend information related to the quality of a solid surface. An important parameter of surface integrity is surface roughness and it is the measure of macro and micro asperities and irregularities on a finished surface after machining (Sadilek *et al.*, 2015; Sathisha *et al.*, 2016; Astakhov, 2020). Basic industrial requirements of machined parts such as appearance, corrosion resistance, wear resistance, fatigue resistance, lubrication, tolerances and ability to hold pressure, can very well be linked to the quality of surface roughness (Sheila, 2009; Tulasiramarao *et al.*, 2014; Liao *et al.*, 2021).

In machining operations, different machine tools such as lathes, drilling machine, horizontal and vertical milling machines etc., are utilised. Of these machining processes, turning still remains the most important operation used to shape metal, because in turning, the conditions of operation are most varied in the modern industry (Pankaj *et al.*, 2017). Turning is a form of machining or a material removal process

which is used to create rotational parts by cutting away unwanted material. The turning process requires a turning machine or lathe, work piece, fixture, and cutting tool. The work piece is a piece of re-shaped material that is secured to the fixture, which itself is attached to the turning machine, and allowed to rotate at high speeds. The cutter is typically a single-point cutting tool that is also secured in the machine. The cutting tool feeds into the rotating work piece and cuts away material in the form of small chips to create the desired shape. In turning, the speed and motion of the cutting tool is specified through several parameters. These parameters are selected for each operation based upon the work piece material, tool material, tool size, and more. The ultimate result in turning operations is to obtain surfaces with high dimensional accuracy, good surface finish and high reliability in its service life. Many factors have been found to affect the quality of turned surfaces but the evidently dominating factors as reported by Prasad (2013), are factors due to machining parameters (speed, feed rate, depth of cut) and the tool geometry (back rake, side rake).

The objective of this paper is to determine the effect of machining parameters on surface roughness while turning 0.3% C steel (medium carbon) using Response Surface Methodology (RSM).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The main material used for this work was steel samples. The steel samples were analysed at the Defence Industry Corporation of Nigeria, (DICON), Kaduna. Results obtained from this analysis indicated that the selected work-piece contain 0.3% carbon indicating a medium carbon category. Other materials and tools used in this research work include data from previous

work on effect of machining parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel using lathe machine, Microsoft Excel, and Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package for design of experiments. Table 1 shows the data that was obtained from the previous work.

Table 2.1: Selected cutting parameters with respective values of surface roughness.

Cutting Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/rev)	Rate of Cut (mm)	Depth of Cut (mm)	Mean Surface Roughness Value (µm)
55	0.15		0.25	1.62
55	0.21		0.35	2.20
200	0.15		0.75	0.52
200	0.21		0.35	3.79
300	0.15		0.25	1.43
300	0.21		0.75	0.95

2.2 Method

The data in Table 2.1 was further expanded using the “Rand function” in Microsoft Excel. Five hundred (500) data points were generated from the original data using this function. These data points were used to perform the analyses in response surface methodology.

In response surface analysis, the design type selected for this study was the central composite rotatable design (CCRD). A Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package for design of experiments was used to analyse and generate model equations for surface roughness. Four different models namely; linear, two

factorial interactions (2FI), quadratic, and cubic were used to analyse the responses and the models were fitted to the experimental data using Design Expert Software. The selected model for design was the quadratic model. Based on this design, twenty (20) data points, extracted from the five hundred (500) data points were used to perform the analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of machining parameters on surface roughness

From Figure 3.1, we find the relative importance of the various input parameters. It is to be noted that a large sensitivity to a parameter suggests

that the system’s performance can drastically change with small variation in the parameter and vice versa. Following this analogy, it is clear that the process input variable, namely, the feed rate has the highest impact on the surface roughness of steel followed by the cuttings speed and then depth of cut. These findings are in sync and resonate with what is found in the literature. For instance, Rafai and Islam (2009) investigated the effects of the cutting speed, feed rate, and the depth of cut on the dimensional accuracy and the surface finish in dry turning of AISI 4340 (30 HRC) steel. The authors reported that the extent of the influence of feed rate on surface roughness

was much higher compared to the influence of the cutting speed and depth of cut. Furthermore, the influence of the three main turning parameters on the machinability of homogenized Al–Cu/TiB₂ MMC was investigated by Senthil *et al.* (2013). The authors noted a significant drop in the surface roughness from 50 to 100 m min⁻¹ cutting speed. Thereafter, the roughness remained more or less constant. The surface roughness value appeared to increase rapidly with increasing feed. The surface roughness was affected only slightly by the increase in the depth of cut.

Figure 3.1: Relative importance of input variables on surface roughness

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3.2 Results on Response Surface Methodology

In selecting a suitable model for the surface roughness value, the highest order polynomial where the additional terms are significant must be taken into consideration. In addition, the selected model must not be biased. Furthermore, consideration was given to insignificant lack of fit and the maximization of the adjusted R^2 and the predicted R^2 . The cubic model is biased and therefore cannot be selected. Lastly, higher coefficient of determination (R^2) with lower standard deviation values are usually considered while choosing the preferred model. Four

different models namely; linear, two factorial interactions (2FI), quadratic, and cubic were used to analyse the responses and the models were fitted to the experimental data using design expert software (Minitab). Considering the model with the highest R^2 and lowest standard deviation, the quadratic model was selected to predict the mean surface roughness of the turning operation. The ANOVA of the chosen model (quadratic) with surface roughness as the response is presented in Table 3.1. Table 3.2 presents the analysis of variance for the response (surface roughness.)

Table 3.1: ANOVA of Response Surface Quadratic Model for Surface Roughness (microns)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	10.76	9	1.20	31.34	< 0.0001	Significant
A-Cutting Speed	0.8696	1	0.8696	22.79	0.0008	
B-Feed Rate	0.1914	1	0.1914	5.02	0.0490	
C-Depth of Cut	0.5006	1	0.5006	13.12	0.0047	
AB	0.0015	1	0.0015	0.0396	0.8462	
AC	0.3240	1	0.3240	8.49	0.0154	
BC	0.0946	1	0.0946	2.48	0.1464	
A ²	5.86	1	5.86	153.72	< 0.0001	
B ²	0.0051	1	0.0051	0.1330	0.7230	
C ²	4.08	1	4.08	107.01	< 0.0001	

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Residual	0.3815	10	0.0381			
Lack of Fit	0.3797	5	0.0759	216.99	<	Significant
Pure Error	0.0018	5	0.0004			0.0001
Cor Total	11.14	19				

Table 3.2: Analysis of Variance for the Response

Source	Df	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F- Value	P- Value
Model	9	10.76	1.20	31.34	0.0001
Cutting Speed	1	0.8696	0.8696	22.79	0.0008
Feed Rate	1	0.1914	0.1914	5.02	0.0490
Depth of Cut	1	0.5006	0.5006	13.12	0.0047
Error	10	0.3815	0.0381		
Lack-of-Fit	5	0.3797	0.0759	216.99	0.0001
Pure Error	5	0.0018	0.0004		
Total	19	11.14			

The model F-value of 31.34 implies that the model is significant. There is only 0.01 % chance that a “Model F- Value” this large could occur due to noise. Values of “Prob > F” than 0.0500 indicate that model terms are significant. In this case, A, B, C, AC, A², C² are significant model terms, where A, B and C represents the cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut respectively (Table 3.1). This implies that the cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut all had significant

effects on the mean surface roughness. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. If there are many insignificant model terms (not counting those required to support hierarchy), model reduction may improve the model. However, this was not necessary for the selected model due to the presence of several significant terms (Sam *et al.*, 2024).

The “Lack-of-Fit F-value” of 216.99 in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 implies the Lack-of-Fit is significant. There is only a 0.01% chance that a “Lack of Fit F-value” this large could occur due to noise. Significant lack of fit is bad as the aim is for the model to fit. “Adeq Precision” measures the signal-to-noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Therefore, the ratio of 18.536 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space. The model was

3.3 Determination of Effect of Machining Parameters on Surface Roughness using RSM

The final regression model for the mean surface roughness is given in Equation 4.4

Surface Roughness =

$$\begin{aligned} & -15.43264 \\ & +0.086699 \quad \text{Cutting Speed} \\ & -32.47273 \quad \text{Feed Rate} \\ & +95.66727 \quad \text{Depth of Cut} \\ & -0.018333 \quad \text{Cutting Speed * Feed Rate} \\ & -0.080500 \quad \text{Cutting Speed * Depth of Cut} \\ & +145.00000 \quad \text{Feed Rate * Depth of Cut} \\ & -0.000193 \quad \text{Cutting Speed}^2 \\ & -63.13131 \quad \text{Feed Rate}^2 \\ & -161.18182 \quad \text{Depth of Cut}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 4.4

In the equation above, the positive terms signify a direct relationship between the independent variables (cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut) and the dependent variable (mean surface roughness). On the contrary, the negative terms signify an inverse relationship between the independent variables and the dependent

significant with a low probability value of 0.0001 and a satisfactory coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.9658$. The high coefficient of determination showed excellent correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable (or response being the mean surface roughness). This implies that all the machining parameters have significant effects on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel.

variable. Thus, it was observed that the cutting speed and the depth of cut had a direct relationship with the mean surface roughness, while the feed rate had an indirect relationship on the mean surface roughness. This implies that increase in cutting speed and depth of cut results in a corresponding increase in the value of the

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mean surface roughness while increase in feed rate results in a decrease in the value of mean surface roughness. Furthermore, from the results obtained from ANOVA, it was found that cutting speed had the most significant effect on the mean surface roughness, followed by depth of cut, and the feed rate. This result seems to agree slightly with the findings of Zeqiri *et al.*

(2018) who documented that increasing cutting speed resulted in the decrease of roughness parameters Ra, Rt and Rz. However, the authors noted that increasing cutting depth also increases the roughness parameters. In their conclusions, there was no mention of the effect of feed rate on roughness parameters.

Surface Roughness (microns)

Design Points:

- Above Surface
 - Below Surface
- 0.78 3.64

X1 = B
 X2 = A

Actual Factor
 C = 0.35

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Surface Roughness (microns)

Design Points:

- Above Surface
- Below Surface
- 0.78 3.64

X1 = B
 X2 = C

Actual Factor

A = 155

Surface Roughness (microns)

Design Points:

- Above Surface
- Below Surface
- 0.78 3.64

X1 = C
 X2 = A

Actual Factor

B = 0.18

Figure: 3.1: Surface plots of the response variable

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Figure 3.2: Interaction plots for Surface Roughness

The surface plot of the response is given in Figure 3.1. Furthermore, the interaction plot of the cutting parameters is presented in Figure 3.2. In Figure 3.2, it is shown that interaction occurs between cutting speed and feed rate when the value of the feed rate is set at 0.180 mm/rev. At 55 rpm, the mean surface roughness gradually increases until it reaches a value of 155 rpm whereby further increase in the values of cutting speed will only result in a sharp decrease in the values of surface roughness. The effect of other

values of the feed rate in this interaction is largely insignificant and thus negligible. From the plot, a similar interaction is observed between cutting speed and depth of cut. Given a depth of cut of 0.35 mm, it is noticed that the cutting speed increases rapidly with increasing surface roughness. However, there is a sharp decline when the cutting speed gets to 155 rpm whereby further increase in the values of cutting speed will lead to a rapid decrease in the values of mean surface roughness. A non-parallel interaction is briefly observed between the feed rate and the depth of cut. At lower values of feed, there is a

gradual decrease in the values of surface roughness when the depth of cut is 0.35 mm. However, this value remains constant even with increasing feed rate (Sam, 2024).

3.4 Optimization of cutting parameters for minimum surface roughness

The criteria variables were set in such a way that the independent variables (cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut) would be within a range or minimum from an economical point of view. The main criteria for constraint optimization was minimum surface roughness. The desired goals for each cutting parameter and response is shown in Table 3.3. In order to optimize the parameters of the turning operation, by numerical optimization which finds a point that

minimises the desirability function; equal importance of “3” was assigned to all the three cutting parameters and its response (surface roughness).

The optimization of the turning operations based on the cutting parameters was carried out using numerical technique in response surface methodology (RSM) with the goals as presented in Table 3.3. The ramp of the optimization process is shown in Figure 3.3 with optimal values of cutting parameters of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut at 254.056 (rpm), 0.183419 (mm/rev) and 0.254583 (mm) respectively. Optimal minimum surface roughness was found to be 0.663487 (microns) and a desirability of 1.00 was obtained.

Table 3.3: Criteria and Output for Numerical Optimization of Cutting Parameters and its effect on Surface Roughness

Surface Roughness Parameters	Unit	Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Optimization Goal	Relative Importance
Cutting Speed	rpm	55.00	255.00	Range	3
Feed Rate	mm/rev	0.15	0.21	Range	3
Depth of Cut	millimetres	0.25	0.45	Range	3
Surface Roughness	microns	0.78	3.64	Minimise	3

Desirability = 1.000

Solution 1 out of 100

Figure 3.3: Optimal values of cutting parameters with minimum surface roughness.

4. CONCLUSION

The determination of the effect of machining parameters on surface roughness using response surface methodology has been carried out and the following conclusions drawn from the research work:

1. It is to be noted that a large sensitivity to a parameter suggests that the system's performance can drastically change with small variation in the parameter and vice versa. Following this analogy, it is clear that the process input variable, namely, the feed rate has the highest impact on the surface roughness of steel

followed by the cutting speed, and then depth of cut. The relative importance of feed rate is 45.91%, cutting speed is 28.94% and depth of cut is 25.15%.

2. The quadratic model was selected to predict the mean surface roughness of the turning operation. The model, F- value of 31.34 implies that the model is significant.

3. Values of "Prob > F" than 0.0500 indicate that model terms are significant, i.e. cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut are all significant effects on the mean surface roughness.

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4. The model was significant with a low probability value of 0.0001 and a satisfactory coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.9658$. The high coefficient of determination showed excellent correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable (or response being the mean surface roughness).

5. It was observed that the cutting speed and the depth of cut had a direct relationship with the mean surface roughness, while the feed rate had an indirect relationship on the mean surface roughness.

6. From the results obtained from ANOVA, it was found that cutting speed had the most significant effect on the mean surface roughness, followed by depth of cut, and the feed rate.

7. At lower values of feed, there is a gradual decrease in the values of surface roughness when the depth of cut is 0.35 mm.

8. Finally the study revealed that with optimal values of cutting parameters of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut at 254.056 (rpm), 0.183419 (mm/rev) and 0.254583 (mm) respectively. Optimal minimum surface roughness was found to be 0.663487 (microns), and a desirability of 1.00 was obtained.

Author Contribution

This is to publicly declare that the four authors of this publication (names listed above) were involved in the conceptualization of this research topic. Prof. Ihom, A.P. the first author was saddled with the responsibility of data curation and assisted by the other three authors with

formal analysis. No outside funding was received for this project. The major financial contributor to this project was the first author. The four authors were jointly involved in the research project; playing various roles as supervisors, investigators and resource providers to enable the project go through the various stages of conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding, investigation, methodology, project administration, resource provision, software provision, supervision, validation, writing original draft and final report, and final paper for publication. This was adopted by all the four members of the research team.

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Data Availability

The data used for this work is available in the University of Uyo, Uyo-Nigeria library, in the M.Eng.degree report submitted to the University. It is also available in journal publication made from the work. The references included in our journal publication are duly referenced. Every second party data used in the publication is duly referenced and credit given to source.

Conflict of Interests

The authors wish to publicly declare that there is no conflict of interest in this publication all the four authors have agreed to submit their work for journal publication.

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Financial Interests

We wish to publicly declare that this is a self-sponsored research work contributed to by the research team members.

Non-Financial Interests

This work is free of all encumbrances, whether financial or non-financial interests

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